

On Thioaldehydes and Thioketones. Part I.

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The simple replacement of the oxygen atom in an aldehyde, *e.g.*, benzaldehyde by sulphur has always resulted in the production of a polymerised body (*cf.* Baumann and Fromm, *Annalen*, 1848, 66, 158 *et seq* ; Klinger and others, *Ber.*, 1877, 10, 1877 *et seq*). Barbaglia and Marquardt's attempt (*Ber.*, 1891, 24, 1881) resulted in a similar failure, benzaldehyde when heated with sulphur gave stilbene and trithiobenzaldehyde.

Benzylidene chloride when condensed with sodium sulphide in the present investigation, furnished a reddish oil which decomposed when distilled in *vacuo* to stilbene.

Ethyl thioacetoacetate and benzaldehyde when condensed in presence of piperidine furnished an oil which solidified (m.p. 82-83°) after 24 hours. The analysis corresponded to a thiobenzaldehyde, probably polymerised. From the mother liquor diethyl benzal-diacetoacetate can be isolated. Hence it seems that ethyl thioacetoacetate parted with the sulphur atom abstracting the oxygen atom from benzaldehyde. The liberated ethyl acetoacetate reacted with benzaldehyde in the normal Knoevenagel way. This is in conformity with the behaviour of this substance, as the sulphur atom is loosely bound. Benzaldehyde does not react with ethyl thioacetoacetate without the condensing agent even on boiling.

The substance (m.p. 82-83°) condenses with phenylhydrazine, methylphenylhydrazine and hydrazine hydrate to give the corresponding benzylidene derivatives which point to the substance not being a thioether. Klinger (*loc. cit.*) and Ruheman (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, 87, 25) isolated a substance having the same m.p. (83-84°), which was regarded as a mixture of various indefinitely polymerised products (*Ber.*, 1891, 24, 1431). The ready reaction of the compound with phenylhydrazine suggests that the molecules are loosely bound in the polymerised product by residual affinity. The substance (m.p. 82-83°) is converted to β -trithiobenzaldehyde of Baumann and Fromm by acid chloride even at 0°.

1481), yield 70 p.c. It is soluble in chloroform, carbon disulphide and piperidine. It dissolves on boiling with alcoholic sodium ethoxide to a deep red solution. A boiling aqueous alcoholic solution of potassium cyanide does not affect it (8 hours). On shaking with metallic mercury or freshly prepared mercuric oxide it gave mercuric sulphide, (Found: C, 68.1; H, 5.2; S, 25.5; M. W. (ebulliscope in chloroform), 814.5. $(C_7H_6S)_7$ requires C, 68.8; H, 4.9; S, 26.2 per cent; M. W., 854).

Ethyl benzaldiacetoacetate.—The decanted supernatant liquid from above was treated with water to just turbidity and on keeping overnight, crystals of ethyl benzaldiacetoacetate began to appear. Recrystallised from alcohol and petroleum ether, it melts at 138°. (Found: C, 65.2; H, 7.1. $C_{19}H_{24}O_6$ requires C, 65.5; H, 6.9 per cent.).

Benzaldehyde-phenylhydrazone.—Thiobenzaldehyde (5 g., 1 mol.) and phenylhydrazine (1 mol.) were heated in a boiling water-bath for 6 hours. When the evolution of hydrogen sulphide ceased, the product was washed with dilute hydrochloric acid and crystallised from alcohol, m. p. 158°, yield 80 p. c. (Found: N, 14.57. $C_{13}H_{12}N_2$ requires N, 14.3 per cent.).

Benzaldehyde-asym-phenylmethylhydrazone.—Thiobenzaldehyde (5 g.) was treated with requisite quantity of phenylmethylhydrazine (asym.). The product was recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 102°, yield almost theoretical. (Found: N, 13.51. $C_{14}H_{14}N_2$ requires N, 13.33 per cent.). It also gave *dibenzalazine* with hydrazine hydrate, m. p. 93°.

Thiobenzaldehyde (Method II).—Benzaldehyde (50 g.) in alcohol (100 c.c.) was treated with piperidine (1 c.c.) and hydrogen sulphide was passed into the mixture. After a short time, the mixture grew hot and the reaction was moderated by cooling in ice. The reaction was completed in 1 hour when most of the thiobenzaldehyde separated as a pasty mass. The product was then kept in a steam oven for 6 hours and finally crystallised from chloroform and alcohol, m. p. 83-84°, yield 90 p.c. Thioanisaldehyde was prepared in a similar manner, m.p. 73-75°.

Action of thiobenzaldehyde on acyl chlorides in presence of piperidine.—A mixture of thiobenzaldehyde (3 g.), piperidine (0.5 c.c.) and chloroform (30 c. c.) was allowed to stand for 6 hours and then treated with benzoyl chloride (1 mol.) and kept at 4° for 4 hours. It gave white crystals, m. p. 226°, identified as β -trithiobenzaldehyde, yield quantitative. Acetyl chloride behaves similarly.

Formation of stilbene from thiobenzaldehyde.—Thiobenzaldehyde (10 g.) dissolved in minimum quantity of chloroform and treated with piperidine (0.5 c. c.) and boiled on the steam bath till the evolution of hydrogen sulphide ceased. The chloroform was removed and the resulting product was extracted with ether; after removal of ether, the oil gave stilbene, m. p. 127°, on vacuum distillation.

Preparation of β -trithiobenzaldehyde.—Ethyl thioacetoacetate (13 g.) and benzaldehyde (10 g.) in alcohol (40 c. c.) were treated with dry hydrochloric acid gas till saturation. The whole mass was kept overnight. Needle-shaped crystals of β -trithiobenzaldehyde collected at the bottom. The product was recrystallised from acetic acid, m. p. 226°, yield 6 g. The m. p. remained unchanged on mixing with β -trithiobenzaldehyde prepared by passing sulphuretted hydrogen through benzaldehyde in alcoholic hydrogen chloride. It did not give any sulphuretted hydrogen when boiled with phenylhydrazine in acetic acid, in pyridine and in pyridine with a trace of piperidine.

o-Nitrothiobenzaldehyde.—*o*-Nitrobenzaldehyde (10 g.) in alcohol (50 c. c.) containing ethyl thioacetoacetate (11 g.) was treated at 0° with dry hydrogen chloride till saturation. After 3 hours a white precipitate separated. It was filtered off, washed free from acid with rectified spirit and then with alcohol and ether. It was purified by dissolving in pyridine and precipitating by means of ether, m. p. 163–72°, yield 9 g. (Found: N, 8.2; S, 19.2. $C_7H_5O_2NS$ requires N, 8.38; S, 19.16 per cent.).

o-Nitrothiobenzaldehyde is insoluble in almost all organic solvents excepting pyridine. On standing it transformed into plastic state and finally resinified. In pyridine solution in presence of few drops of piperidine it gave with phenylhydrazine the phenylhydrozone, m. p. 156° with evolution of sulphuretted hydrogen. (Found: N, 17.3. $C_{13}H_{11}O_2N_3$ requires N, 17.4 per cent.).

m-Nitrothiobenzaldehyde was prepared from *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde (5 g.) under similar conditions as the preceding compound. Its method of purification and properties are also similar to the *ortho* analogue. It shrinks at 110° and melts at 185–90°. (Found: N, 8.4; S, 18.9. $C_7H_5O_2NS$ requires N, 8.38; S, 19.16 per cent.).

Thioanisaldehyde.—An alcoholic solution (40 c. c.) of anisaldehyde (10 g.) and ethyl thioacetoacetate (20 g.) was saturated at 0° with HCl for 20 minutes and kept for 4 hours. After addition of water (4 c. c.) the pasty mass was washed with alcohol and extracted

with ether and ether removed. It was further purified by precipitating from hot alcohol, m. p. 73–76°, yield 4 g.

It can also be prepared with better yield (8 g.) by following the first method of preparation of thiobenzaldehyde. It is fairly soluble in ether, chloroform, pyridine and benzene, but sparingly soluble in cold alcohol. It gives phenylhydrazone, m. p. 120°. (Found: C, 65·3; H, 5·4; S, 20·8; M. W. (ebulliscope in CHCl_3), 1690. $(\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{OS})_{11}$ requires C, 63·15; H, 5·26; S, 21·05 per cent; M. W., 1672).

Thioacetophenone.— A mixture of acetophenone (50 g.) and ethyl thioacetate (70 g.) in alcohol (100 c.c.) was saturated at 0° with HCl, allowed to stand for 10 hours and then treated with crushed ice. The oily product was extracted with ether, washed with sodium carbonate solution and dehydrated over calcium chloride. The oil on removing the ether was distilled in vacuum. The distillate between 100–125° on repeated fractionation gave a dark violet oil, b. p. 110/20 mm., yield 5 g. It is a deep violet unstable liquid possessing garlic odour. On keeping the colour disappears. Unlike the thioaldehydes it reacts with phenylhydrazine in cold with the formation of a phenylhydrazone, m. p. 102°. (Found: C, 70·2; H, 6·05; S, 23·3. $\text{C}_8\text{H}_8\text{S}$ requires C, 70·58; H, 5·88; S, 23·5 per cent.).

Thiobenzophenone was prepared from benzophenone (10 g.) and ethyl thioacetoacetate (15 g.) and purified in the same way as the preceding compound. The resulting oil was distilled in vacuum and the fraction collected between 100–170° at 10 mm. on repeated fractionation gave a dark blue oil, b. p. 175/10 mm., yield 3 g. (Found: C, 78·5; H, 5·1; S, 16·2; M. W., 213. $\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{10}\text{S}$ requires C, 78·7; H, 5·05; S, 16·16 per cent; M. W., 198).

In conclusion the author wishes to convey his grateful thanks to Sir P. C. Ráy for his kind interest and encouragement during this investigation.

